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Workpackage 2

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Contributing partners: BfR, SVA, VFL/EMU, WBVR/UU, ANSES, AGES/VMU, VRI, NDRVMI, ISS, IZSAM, IZSLER, RIVM

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BIOPIGEE

Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at farm

Participating countries

UK (APHA), PL (PIWET), AT (AGES/VMU), SE (SVA), DE (BfR), IT (IZSLER, IZSAM, ISS), BG (NDRVMI), CZ (VRI), NL (RIVM), EE (VFL/EMU), FR (ANSES), NL (WBVR/UU)

Background

Salmonella and hepatitis E virus (HEV) are zoonotic pathogens that typically cause subclinical infections in pigs but cause gastrointestinal infections in humans. Understanding which on-farm biosecurity measures have a substantial effect in reducing the presence of these pathogens is important to help advise farmers on how to control their introduction and transmission. Biosecurity protocols are important tools to identify optimal and suboptimal practices on pig farms, and advise on improvements that can be made, which would have the most effectiveness in reducing the threat of infectious pathogens.

Aim and objective

The aim of this task was to identify biosecurity measures that are relevant for *Salmonella* and HEV occurrence and their spread within pig production in order to determine best practice with regards to these pathogens. To achieve this, the study aimed to select a pig farm population that was representative of farming in the participating countries. Each farm was surveyed to collect information on biosecurity measures and samples were collected to understand the *Salmonella* and HEV risk. The data from each farm was used for an epidemiological risk factor analysis to quantify the effect of each biosecurity measure.

Methods

Farm enrolment

Three farm types selected to cover most pig farm types in the study were defined as 1) fattening, 2) breeding and 3) farrow-to-finish units. It was agreed that small holdings (those within the bottom 5% of national herd size) would not be enrolled into the study. Outdoor farms were included for countries where these farms represent a commercial enterprise and all the pigs for a pig type (e.g. breeding or finishing pigs) were kept outdoors. Farms in which some pigs from a specific pig type were kept indoors and some were outdoors were excluded from the study due to difficulties in equating protocol information to the risk of these farms. For breeding farms, only herds which supply pigs that will go to farms to finish them for slaughter were targeted for inclusion and nucleus/multiplier herds which only produce replacement breeding pigs for breeding farms were excluded. Finally, SPF (specific pathogen free) farms were excluded from the study. Nucleus/multiplier and SPF herds are few in number and are special classes of farm, which are difficult for visitors to get allowance to access.

The selection of farms was to try (where possible) to represent the most common sizes and types of farming in each country, and also to try and select farms with expected high and low *Salmonella* or HEV risk. However, in most instances the farm selection was simply a convenience sample of those farms willing to participate.

Protocol design

The questions to include in the protocol related to external and internal biosecurity applied on pig farms and also included disinfection methods. The selection of questions was guided by literature searches and expert opinion. The protocol included questions on the economics of production and costs of veterinary services, which were used for other parts of the project and are not discussed further in this report. The protocol was limited in size and scope (i.e. the number of biosecurity questions could not exceed 60 and the total number of questions could not exceed 100), because filling in such a form with too many questions would in many cases be difficult or even impossible and would limit recruitment. The completed protocol was sent to representatives of individual EU countries to be translated into their native language.

How the data was collected in the protocol was an important point. It was agreed that the protocol should be accessible in an electronic form, and answers to questions were to be completed by BIOPIGEE staff or subcontractors in an interview style with the farmers or veterinarians taking care of the pigs. Each recruited farm was asked to complete the biosecurity protocol (<https://zenodo.org/record/5336900#.YaC6wytxc2w>). Although it was planned to complete the protocol face-to-face, due to COVID-19 restrictions, these were also completed over phone conversations.

Sample collection

As a result of extensive consultations with both HEV and *Salmonella* experts, the optimal number of faecal samples, and which age groups will be sampled, was determined. The sampling frame was determined as a cost-efficient method to identify and stratify farms as either high or low risk for these two pathogens. Ultimately, it was determined that 20 pooled faecal samples (with 10 individual samples per pooled sample) will be collected at each farm which would provide sufficient sensitivity to detect at least one positive sample from a range of expected farm-prevalence according to an earlier statistical analysis. Most experts agreed that fresh faecal samples should be collected from fattening pigs in the period before the average age of slaughter (~4 months). In the case of breeding females, the preferred target group would be gilts (80% of samples taken) and, to a lesser extent, dry sows (20% of samples taken). This was agreed as optimal for the two pathogens according to the results from previously conducted studies on the occurrence of HEV and *Salmonella* in pig farms. On a farrow-to-finish farm the number of samples to be collected was split between 1) the finishing pigs around 4 months old (10 pooled faecal samples), 2) dry sows (2 pooled faecal samples) and 3) gilts (8 pooled faecal samples). In addition, it was recommended that faecal samples were best collected from as many different pens as possible. Samples should be taken from fresh faeces, preferably after defecation, with each individual sample containing a minimum of 10g of faeces. Gloves were changed between pooled samples.

Sample testing

The project experts expressed a common position regarding the transport of samples and their storage. It was determined that fresh faeces would be transported to the laboratory in a cool box (to stop temperatures exceeding 25°C) and tested as soon as possible (e.g. within 48 hours after collection) with guidance taken from ISO 13307:2013. Upon arrival the samples were divided for *Salmonella* and HEV diagnostics. All laboratories from the project team agreed that *Salmonella* detection and identification will follow the EN ISO 6579-1:2017-04 standard. The testing for *Salmonella* was performed without any further storage, hence subsamples for HEV isolation were deep-frozen. After the completed tests, all laboratories entered their results into the sample record forms containing the following data: farm ID, sample collection date, farm type, sample ID number, pig type (dry sow, gilt, finisher, estimated age of finishers (months), barn/outdoor enclosure ID, pen/outdoor section ID, number of individual samples collected per pooled sample, and estimated number of pigs in pen. Individual laboratories filled in forms concerning the results of laboratory tests. In the case of *Salmonella*, the following data was completed: farm ID, sample collection date, sample ID number, tested after 48 hours of collection (Y/N), sample frozen or not, result achieved after 24 or 48 hr incubation, final result +/-, and *Salmonella* serovar. For HEV the data was as follows: farm ID, sample collection date, sample ID number, date of RNA extraction/PCR, was sample or RNA frozen prior to PCR, Ct value and recovery rate for process control.

Data analysis and risk categorisation

The protocol responses were reviewed and cleaned, with potentially incorrect information checked with the farmer or the local project team. Where possible, unanswered protocol data was reported as 'missing', or "Not Applicable" where appropriate, to allow these records to be retained in the multivariable model, whilst accounting for these missing records as separate from the other responses.

To generate a binary outcome response for both of the two pathogens, a profile of lab results from all of the farms was assessed whilst taking into account deviations from the sampling protocols (e.g. *Salmonella* samples tested after 48 hours of collection, age of finishers or less pools collected per sample), types of pigs sampled (finishers, gilts and sows) and also seasonal factors (month or season of sample collection). A cut-off value to define high and low risk for each pathogen was agreed by the project team after assessing a plot of the proportion of positive samples from all the farms.

Multivariable analysis, using a forwards-stepwise logistic regression (logistic command) model, was used to estimate the statistical significance of associations between exposure variables and the binary pathogen risk status, whilst accounting for the presence of other variables included in the model. At the initial stage, a screening univariable stage was used and all variables with a P-value less than 0.25 were excluded from the model. In subsequent steps, the significant variable (P-value<0.05) that most improved the fit of the model (lowest AIC) was included until a step was reached where no further variables were significant or could improve the model fit. All data analyses were conducted using Stata 15 (StataCorp. 2017. *Stata Statistical Software: Release 15*. College Station, TX: StataCorp LLC).

Results

A total of 264 questionnaires were received, although 14 farms could not be linked to *Salmonella* results (i.e. samples were not tested for *Salmonella*). Between 18 and 38 questionnaires and *Salmonella* results were received from each of nine European countries. The analysis of the *Salmonella*

sample level results indicated that positive results were more likely from gilts than other sampled pig types and from finisher pigs aged three months old in comparison to older finisher pigs. Sample results from these two categories were adjusted to ensure a more consistent appraisal of risk between all the farms from the various farm types included in the study. Of the 250 questionnaires available for *Salmonella* analysis, 41 (16%) were rated as high risk. Some HEV testing results were still pending, due to delays incurred by the COVID-19 pandemic, and the HEV risk factor analysis will be completed at a later date (see further work).

Although questionnaires covered all seven farm types in the eligible for the study, 77% were either farrow-to-finish or finisher farms. Only five farms included in the study used outdoor production and these came from two countries. The results indicated that a relatively large number of the questionnaire variables were associated with farms being high risk for *Salmonella* at the univariable screening step, but few variables entered the final multivariable model, whilst accounting for the effect of the other variables in the model.

Conclusion

This study utilised a comprehensive list of individual measures and a robust population of pig farms from across Europe. The results have highlighted the importance of biosecurity measures in controlling *Salmonella* on pig farms in Europe, with a wide range of different biosecurity measures having a significant association with farms being at high risk from *Salmonella*. The multivariable results indicated which variables may be the most important, although some of these may be proxies for combinations of factors, and further analysis (e.g. factor analysis) may be needed in order to help characterise the difference in application of biosecurity on high and low risk farms. This work has built upon the evidence gathered through previous studies of biosecurity and will assist in identifying the most efficient *Salmonella* control measures.

Future work

Further analysis of the *Salmonella* results will be completed. This study will be continued by an analysis of the HEV risk factors, using the same statistical methods. *These results will be completed and added to the final deliverable by 28/02/2022.*

Additional analysis will be completed using any additional 120 farms from two additional countries, which reported *Salmonella* or HEV results but only included a more limited number of biosecurity factors. The results from these analyses will be used to inform risk assessments and cost-benefit analysis which have been designed within this project.

A publication of the questionnaire and the survey results in a scientific journal is planned.

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